

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATION LEVEL AND ATTITUDE TOWARD TAX EVASION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Several studies have examined the relationship between attitude toward tax evasion and the level of education. However, those studies were limited to a single country. The results have been mixed. In some cases, tax evasion was found to be more acceptable among the less educated group. In other studies, the exact opposite was found. A third group of studies found no significant relationship between education level and the acceptability of tax evasion. The present study uses data from the most recent World Values Survey, which interviewed more than 125,000 people in nearly 80 countries. The survey included a question on attitude toward tax evasion. This study examines this data with the goal of determining if there is a significant relationship between education level and attitude toward tax evasion.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies have been conducted over the years on attitudes toward tax evasion, and the arguments that have been used to justify it. Crowe (1944) examined the Christian (mostly Catholic) literature. Some of the literature went back several hundred years, and was in the Latin language. Some of the most frequently cited reasons to justify tax evasion were in cases where there was an inability to pay, where the government was corrupt, where tax rates were too high, or where the government wasted a large portion of the tax funds raised. He generally took the position that there is a moral duty to pay just taxes, but there was less of a moral duty to pay unjust taxes.

Pennock (1998) discussed the morality of paying taxes to support an unjust war. McGee (2012), in several surveys, asked whether it would be ethical for a Jew living in Nazi Germany to evade paying taxes to Hitler. In other places he asked whether tax evasion is unethical (McGee, 1994), and what constitutes paying one's fair share (McGee, 1999, 2004).

The literature of various religions has been examined to determine what guidance might be found. The Jewish literature generally frowns on tax evasion, but makes limited exceptions for cases where the government is corrupt (Cohn, 1998, 2012; Tamari, 1998). Schansberg (1998) examined the Christian Biblical literature and determined that there are limits to what one is morally obligated to render to the state. Gronbacher (1998) took the position that the use to which the tax funds are put has a relationship to the justifiability of evasion. Tax systems where a main goal is redistribution need not be supported as enthusiastically as tax systems where the funds are used for the defense of life, liberty and property only. Green (2020) examined the morality of head, proportional and progressive taxation from both the Jewish and Christian perspectives.

Smith & Kimball (1998) examined the Mormon literature but could not find a single case where tax evasion could be justified. However, a survey of Mormon students found them to be more flexible on the issue of tax evasion (McGee & Smith, 2012). The Baha'i faith allows tax

evasion only in cases where a member of the Baha'i faith is persecuted by the government (DeMerville, 1998).

The Islamic literature that is available in the English language seems to be at opposite ends of the spectrum. Some Islamic scholars interpret the Islamic literature to approve of tax evasion in any case where the result would be raising prices, such as would a sales or value added tax or a tariff. They would also justify the evasion of taxes on income (Ahmad, 1995; Yusuf, 1971). Jalili (2012), on the other hand, interprets the Islamic literature to prohibit tax evasion in all cases, but only if the country is governed by Sharia law. He evades the question of what would be ethically appropriate in cases where the country is not governed by Sharia law.

The classical public finance literature basically ignores the possibility that tax evasion might be justified in certain cases, and merely discusses the various forms of taxation and which ones might be better or worse than others (Musgrave, 1959, 1986; Musgrave & Peacock, 1958; Buchanan, 1967; Buchanan & Musgrave, 2001), a point that Block (1989) has raised.

Some scholars have challenged the very justifiability of taxation, at least in some cases (Block & Torsell, 2020; Chodorov, 1962). Others have criticized the morality of the graduated income tax, mostly on the basis of utilitarian ethics (Blum & Kalven, 1953), and the morality of redistribution (Jouvenel, 1952). Other scholars have examined various moral aspects of taxation (Bird-Pollan, 2020; Frecknall-Hughes, 2020; Gribnau & Dijkstra, 2020; van Brederode, 2020). Nozick (1974) likens the income tax to a form of slavery, since it confiscates a portion of the fruits of one's labor.

Goerke (2013) concluded that the reason why individuals of different education levels have different views toward the acceptability of tax evasion is primarily driven by their income level. Individuals who have high incomes tend to have more education than individuals with lower incomes because income is partially determined by education level. The question then remains, what is the relationship between income level and attitude toward the acceptability of tax evasion.

That question remains unanswered (McGee, 2012). Although several studies have been conducted to determine the relationship between income level and attitude toward tax evasion, the results have been mixed (McGee, 2012). Some studies, summarized in McGee (2012) found that there is a positive correlation, whereas other studies found the correlation to be negative. A third set of studies found the relationship to be either curvilinear or not determinable.

The most comprehensive study of the correlation between education and views on the acceptability of tax evasion was conducted by McGee (2012a). That study used a prior series of World Values Survey data, and found that there was a positive correlation in some countries, a negative correlation in other countries, and a curvilinear correlation in a third group of countries, while no correlation existed in other countries. However, he did not examine which of the correlations was dominant. The present study uses more recent data and does determine which correlation is dominant.

METHODOLOGY

Every five years or so, starting in 1981, the people who publish the World Values Surveys (Haerper, 2020) conduct individual face-to-face interviews with a wide range of individuals from different educational, social, and religious backgrounds. The latest, Wave 7, asked hundreds of questions to more than 125,000 individuals in nearly 80 countries. One of those questions asked about the justifiability of tax evasion. The interviewer asked respondents to choose a number from 1 to 10 to indicate whether tax evasion was never justified (1) to always justified (10). Not every question was asked in every country. The tax evasion question was asked in 76 countries.

In this study, we examined the relationship between education level and attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion. The database divided education level into three groups – lower, middle and higher – without going into much detail about where the cut-off might be separating any of the categories. We determined whether the differences between levels of education were significant using a two-tailed student t-test that compared the mean, standard deviation and sample size of the two groups that had the lowest and highest mean scores. The results are presented below.

FINDINGS

The present study found that several correlations exist, and that one correlation is dominant. Table 1 lists all 76 of the countries included in the database and shows the means, standard deviations and sample sizes for each of the three education levels. P values were also calculated.

Table 1
Relationship between Acceptability of Tax Evasion and Education Level
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Albania	1.59	1.64	804	1.68	1.86	497	1.62	1.67	154	0.3613
Andorra	1.64	1.59	295	1.73	1.56	292	1.67	1.53	416	0.4891
Argentina	2.21	1.98	563	2.11	1.98	313	1.87	1.59	127	0.0711
Armenia	3.88	3.01	339	3.89	3.10	1,156	3.52	3.12	6	0.7706
Australia	1.94	2.15	127	1.93	1.72	1,152	2.15	1.91	459	0.0250
Austria	1.70	1.44	323	1.91	1.76	849	1.82	1.58	469	0.0558
Azerbaijan	3.16	2.75	275	2.96	2.67	1,303	2.94	2.76	239	0.3669
Bangladesh	1.71	1.14	943	1.68	1.07	153	1.61	1.04	103	0.3942
Belarus	2.97	2.14	79	3.35	2.45	418	3.24	2.43	1,050	0.1981
Bolivia	1.98	1.95	709	2.17	2.00	633	1.98	1.94	719	0.0786
Bosnia & Herzegovina	1.57	1.70	608	1.90	2.17	891	1.70	2.08	218	0.0017
Brazil	2.95	3.09	720	3.12	2.99	735	2.81	2.59	279	0.1269
Bulgaria	1.72	1.91	383	1.61	1.57	-900	1.61	1.55	274	0.4322
Chile	3.53	2.70	263	2.22	1.98	524	2.48	2.18	211	0.0001
China	1.51	1.27	1,952	1.34	1.06	543	1.63	1.54	505	0.0004
Colombia	2.21	2.39	574	2.02	2.13	594	1.86	1.99	330	0.0247
Croatia	1.50	1.55	450	2.28	2.55	787	2.08	2.06	243	0.0001
Cyprus	1.32	0.96	277	1.43	1.31	331	1.78	1.89	375	0.0002

Czech Republic	2.01	1.96	361	2.10	1.96	1,134	2.17	1.95	316	0.2885
Denmark	1.62	1.51	892	1.60	1.26	1,339	1.51	1.26	1,059	0.0796
Ecuador	2.55	2.63	377	2.32	2.34	517	2.10	2.11	303	0.0159
Egypt	1.60	1.42	496	1.55	1.27	452	1.39	1.23	252	0.0461
Estonia	2.05	2.10	216	2.17	2.02	615	2.15	1.92	472	0.4575
Ethiopia	1.69	2.29	803	1.27	1.28	241	1.32	1.44	180	0.0066
Finland	1.56	1.34	09	1.97	1.79	518	1.76	1.31	385	0.4946
France	2.05	1.87	860	2.16	1.97	426	1.90	1.73	590	0.0260
Georgia	2.58	2.57	274	2.29	2.12	1,290	1.97	1.94	645	0.0001
Germany – East & West	1.56	1.57	430	1.49	1.30	1,942	1.68	1.44	1,305	0.0001
Greece	1.50	1.15	474	1.74	1.52	481	1.89	1.79	245	0.0004
Hong Kong	1.69	1.47	715	2.22	1.88	786	2.59	2.05	572	0.0001
Hungary	1.52	1.65	359	1.48	1.21	824	1.61	1.36	328	0.1127
Iceland	1.81	1.67	496	1.75	1.39	569	1.90	1.52	549	0.0852
Indonesia	2.95	2.93	2,024	2.04	1.88	817	1.76	1.56	356	0.0001
Iran	2.33	2.47	378	2.45	2.4	555	2.21	2.30	561	0.0884
Iraq	2.75	2.18	623	2.94	2.26	264	2.55	2.12	310	0.0335
Italy	2.22	2.04	1,218	2.00	1.85	747	1.74	1.58	300	0.0001
Japan	1.47	1.43	84	1.23	0.91	515	1.25	0.92	738	0.0416
Jordan	2.04	2.15	423	2.12	2.37	475	2.17	2.29	303	0.4346
Kazakhstan	2.67	2.49	73	3.13	2.57	461	2.82	2.46	693	0.1542
Kyrgyzstan	3.19	3.33	85	2.08	2.14	585	2.28	2.59	529	0.0001
Lebanon	2.61	1.97	388	2.56	2.13	371	2.52	2.08	441	0.5242
Lithuania	2.56	2.07	386	2.74	2.21	470	2.76	2.21	590	0.1567
Macau	2.38	1.87	303	2.25	1.77	288	2.19	1.71	408	0.1597
Malaysia	3.49	2.58	686	3.29	2.46	245	3.34	2.45	382	0.2921
Mexico	2.94	2.56	529	3.04	2.61	857	2.91	2.54	345	0.4313
Montenegro	2.23	1.98	288	1.86	1.59	533	1.85	2.01	177	0.0463
Myanmar	1.73	1.51	755	1.49	1.29	309	1.33	0.85	134	0.0029
Netherlands	2.21	1.93	755	2.15	1.83	923	2.09	1.69	692	0.2103
New Zealand	1.70	1.78	161	1.65	1.41	274	1.87	1.62	591	0.0535
Nicaragua	2.31	2.59	652	2.09	2.23	288	1.99	2.27	259	0.0821
Nigeria	1.79	1.64	483	1.78	1.60	624	1.81	1.81	120	0.8540
North Macedonia	2.05	2.11	357	1.62	1.69	554	1.58	1.52	198	0.0059
Norway	1.86	1.89	283	1.69	1.51	440	1.58	1.31	378	0.0249
Pakistan	1.93	2.00	1,088	2.08	2.26	697	1.79	1.97	207	0.0958
Peru	1.90	1.91	349	1.82	1.64	702	1.85	1.79	350	0.4814
Philippines	4.12	3.07	889	4.39	3.22	143	3.34	2.82	168	0.0024
Poland	1.49	1.36	566	1.63	1.58	415	1.58	1.36	369	0.1374
Puerto Rico	1.46	1.59	169	1.46	1.56	316	1.56	1.67	642	0.4845
Romania	2.42	2.60	1,496	2.72	2.86	807	2.20	2.33	492	0.0007
Russian Federation	3.82	2.99	974	3.78	2.91	983	3.72	2.75	1,677	0.3823
Serbia	2.11	2.29	926	2.62	2.87	1,027	3.15	3.28	588	0.0001
Slovakia	2.90	1.92	162	2.75	2.26	1,011	2.28	1.83	254	0.0010
Slovenia	1.75	1.62	218	1.81	1.66	600	1.70	1.51	257	0.3616
South Korea	2.35	1.62	140	2.25	1.54	522	2.17	1.50	583	0.2099
Spain	2.81	2.76	620	3.04	2.74	227	2.63	2.62	356	0.0709
Sweden	2.01	1.64	213	1.78	1.48	523	1.48	1.06	448	0.0001

Switzerland	2.23	2.23	753	2.01	1.83	1,420	1.86	1.58	955	0.0001
Taiwan ROC	1.68	1.16	289	1.68	1.56	349	1.79	1.47	585	0.2663
Tajikistan	2.65	1.60	137	2.31	1.49	564	2.43	1.61	488	0.0185
Thailand	1.76	1.38	982	1.86	1.73	264	1.54	1.27	231	0.0209
Tunisia	2.08	2.01	550	1.78	1.54	481	1.77	1.73	161	0.0765
Turkey	1.64	1.53	1,120	1.74	1.75	283	1.72	1.72	1,003	0.3406
United Kingdom	1.86	1.76	677	1.72	1.62	403	1.66	1.46	704	0.0215
United States	3.18	3.00	40	2.02	1.95	1,052	1.98	1.69	1,111	0.0001
Vietnam	2.81	2.01	390	2.82	2.08	539	2.90	2.09	271	0.5777
Zimbabwe	1.85	2.33	681	1.79	1.96	441	2.20	2.44	91	0.0047

Table 2 lists the 38 countries where the education level demographic is not significant at the 10 percent level.

Table 2
Countries Where Education Level is Not Significant (10%)
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Albania	1.59	1.64	804	1.68	1.86	497	1.62	1.67	154	0.3613
Andorra	1.64	1.59	295	1.73	1.56	292	1.67	1.53	416	0.4891
Austria	1.70	1.44	323	1.91	1.76	849	1.82	1.58	469	0.0558
Azerbaijan	3.16	2.75	275	2.96	2.67	1,303	2.94	2.76	239	0.3669
Bangladesh	1.71	1.14	943	1.68	1.07	153	1.61	1.04	103	0.3942
Belarus	2.97	2.14	79	3.35	2.45	418	3.24	2.43	1,050	0.1981
Bosnia & Herzegovina	1.57	1.70	608	1.90	2.17	891	1.70	2.08	218	0.0017
Brazil	2.95	3.09	720	3.12	2.99	735	2.81	2.59	279	0.1269
Bulgaria	1.72	1.91	383	1.61	1.57	-900	1.61	1.55	274	0.4322
Czech Republic	2.01	1.96	361	2.10	1.96	1,134	2.17	1.95	316	0.2885
Denmark	1.62	1.51	892	1.60	1.26	1,339	1.51	1.26	1,059	0.0796
Egypt	1.60	1.42	496	1.55	1.27	452	1.39	1.23	252	0.0461
Estonia	2.05	2.10	216	2.17	2.02	615	2.15	1.92	472	0.4575
Finland	1.56	1.34	09	1.97	1.79	518	1.76	1.31	385	0.4946
France	2.05	1.87	860	2.16	1.97	426	1.9	1.73	590	0.0260
Hungary	1.52	1.65	359	1.48	1.21	824	1.61	1.36	328	0.1127
Iceland	1.81	1.67	496	1.75	1.39	569	1.90	1.52	549	0.0852
Jordan	2.04	2.15	423	2.12	2.37	475	2.17	2.29	303	0.4346
Kazakhstan	2.67	2.49	73	3.13	2.57	461	2.82	2.46	693	0.1542
Lebanon	2.61	1.97	388	2.56	2.13	371	2.52	2.08	441	0.5242
Lithuania	2.56	2.07	386	2.74	2.21	470	2.76	2.21	590	0.1567
Macau	2.38	1.87	303	2.25	1.77	288	2.19	1.71	408	0.1597
Malaysia	3.49	2.58	686	3.29	2.46	245	3.34	2.45	382	0.2921
Mexico	2.94	2.56	529	3.04	2.61	857	2.91	2.54	345	0.4313
Netherlands	2.21	1.93	755	2.15	1.83	923	2.09	1.69	692	0.2103
New Zealand	1.70	1.78	161	1.65	1.41	274	1.87	1.62	591	0.0535
Nigeria	1.79	1.64	483	1.78	1.60	624	1.81	1.81	120	0.8540
Peru	1.90	1.91	349	1.82	1.64	702	1.85	1.79	350	0.4814
Poland	1.49	1.36	566	1.63	1.58	415	1.58	1.36	369	0.1374

Puerto Rico	1.46	1.59	169	1.46	1.56	316	1.56	1.67	642	0.4845
Russian Federation	3.82	2.99	974	3.78	2.91	983	3.72	2.75	1,677	0.3823
Slovakia	2.90	1.92	162	2.75	2.26	1,011	2.28	1.83	254	0.0010
Slovenia	1.75	1.62	218	1.81	1.66	600	1.70	1.51	257	0.3616
South Korea	2.35	1.62	140	2.25	1.54	522	2.17	1.50	583	0.2099
Taiwan ROC	1.68	1.16	289	1.68	1.56	349	1.79	1.47	585	0.2663
Turkey	1.64	1.53	1,120	1.74	1.75	283	1.72	1.72	1,003	0.3406
Vietnam	2.81	2.01	390	2.82	2.08	539	2.90	2.09	271	0.5777
Zimbabwe	1.85	2.33	681	1.79	1.96	441	2.20	2.44	91	0.0047

Table 3 lists the 5 countries where acceptability of tax evasion increases significantly (10%) as the education level increases. The countries included in the list are geographically diverse, coming from Europe, Asia and Oceania.

Table 3
Countries Where Acceptability Increases as Education Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Australia	1.94	2.15	127	1.93	1.72	1,152	2.15	1.91	459	0.0250
Cyprus	1.32	0.96	277	1.43	1.31	331	1.78	1.89	375	0.0002
Greece	1.50	1.15	474	1.74	1.52	481	1.89	1.79	245	0.0004
Hong Kong	1.69	1.47	715	2.22	1.88	786	2.59	2.05	572	0.0001
Serbia	2.11	2.29	926	2.62	2.87	1,027	3.15	3.28	588	0.0001

Table 4 lists the 19 countries where acceptability of tax evasion decreases significantly (10%) as the education level increases. Five of the countries are from Latin America, three from Asia, eight from Europe, two from Africa, and one from North America.

Table 4
Countries Where Acceptability Decreases as Education Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Argentina	2.21	1.98	563	2.11	1.98	313	1.87	1.59	127	0.0711
Chile	3.53	2.70	263	2.22	1.98	524	2.48	2.18	211	0.0001
Colombia	2.21	2.39	574	2.02	2.13	594	1.86	1.99	330	0.0247
Ecuador	2.55	2.63	377	2.32	2.34	517	2.10	2.11	303	0.0159
Ethiopia	1.69	2.29	803	1.27	1.28	241	1.32	1.44	180	0.0066
Georgia	2.58	2.57	274	2.29	2.12	1,290	1.97	1.94	645	0.0001
Indonesia	2.95	2.93	2,024	2.04	1.88	817	1.76	1.56	356	0.0001
Italy	2.22	2.04	1,218	2.00	1.85	747	1.74	1.58	300	0.0001
Japan	1.47	1.43	84	1.23	0.91	515	1.25	0.92	738	0.0416
Montenegro	2.23	1.98	288	1.86	1.59	533	1.85	2.01	177	0.0463
Myanmar	1.73	1.51	755	1.49	1.29	309	1.33	0.85	134	0.0029
Nicaragua	2.31	2.59	652	2.09	2.23	288	1.99	2.27	259	0.0821
North Macedonia	2.05	2.11	357	1.62	1.69	554	1.58	1.52	198	0.0059

Norway	1.86	1.89	283	1.69	1.51	440	1.58	1.31	378	0.0249
Sweden	2.01	1.64	213	1.78	1.48	523	1.48	1.06	448	0.0001
Switzerland	2.23	2.23	753	2.01	1.83	1,420	1.86	1.58	955	0.0001
Tunisia	2.08	2.01	550	1.78	1.54	481	1.77	1.73	161	0.0765
United Kingdom	1.86	1.76	677	1.72	1.62	403	1.66	1.46	704	0.0215
United States	3.18	3.00	40	2.02	1.95	1,052	1.98	1.69	1,111	0.0001

Table 5 lists the nine countries where acceptability of tax evasion increases, then decreases significantly (10%) as the education level increases. Five of the countries are in Asia, three are in Europe, and one is in Latin America.

Table 5
Countries Where Acceptability Increases, then Decreases as Education Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Bolivia	1.98	1.95	709	2.17	2.00	633	1.98	1.94	719	0.0786
Croatia	1.50	1.55	450	2.28	2.55	787	2.08	2.06	243	0.0001
Iran	2.33	2.47	378	2.45	2.4	555	2.21	2.30	561	0.0884
Iraq	2.75	2.18	623	2.94	2.26	264	2.55	2.12	310	0.0335
Pakistan	1.93	2.00	1,088	2.08	2.26	697	1.79	1.97	207	0.0958
Philippines	4.12	3.07	889	4.39	3.22	143	3.34	2.82	168	0.0024
Romania	2.42	2.60	1,496	2.72	2.86	807	2.20	2.33	492	0.0007
Spain	2.81	2.76	620	3.04	2.74	227	2.63	2.62	356	0.0709
Thailand	1.76	1.38	982	1.86	1.73	264	1.54	1.27	231	0.0209

Table 6 lists the 5 countries where acceptability of tax evasion decreases, then increases significantly (10%) as the education level increases. The one common feature of these countries is that some segment of their populations has experienced living under a dictatorship. China and Zimbabwe are currently dictatorships. The Eastern part of Germany was a satellite of the Soviet Union before the dismantling of the Berlin Wall in 1989. Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan were Soviet republics until the implosion of the Soviet Union in 1991. Three of the countries are in Asia, one is in Africa and one is in Europe.

Table 6
Countries Where Acceptability Decreases, then Increases as Education Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P Value
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
China	1.51	1.27	1,952	1.34	1.06	543	1.63	1.54	505	0.0004
Germany – East & West	1.56	1.57	430	1.49	1.30	1,942	1.68	1.44	1,305	0.0001
Kyrgyzstan	3.19	3.33	85	2.08	2.14	585	2.28	2.59	529	0.0001
Tajikistan	2.65	1.6	137	2.31	1.49	564	2.43	1.61	488	0.0185
Zimbabwe	1.85	2.33	681	1.79	1.96	441	2.20	2.44	91	0.0047

Table 7 presents a summary of the findings. If one defines significance at 10 percent, then education is not a significant demographic variable 50 percent of the time. If significance is defined at 5 percent, that percentage rises to 59.2 percent.

In the cases where education is a significant demographic variable, there seems to be four different relationships, the most frequent one being in cases where the acceptability of tax evasion decreases as education level increases.

**Table 7
Summary**

	At 10% Confidence Level		At 5% Confidence Level	
	#	%	#	%
Education is not a significant demographic variable	38	50.0	45	59.2
Acceptability of tax evasion increases as education level increases	5	6.6	5	6.6
Acceptability of tax evasion decreases as education level increases	19	25.0	16	21.1
Acceptability of tax evasion increases, then decreases as education level increases	9	11.8	6	7.9
Acceptability of tax evasion decreases, then increases as education level increases	5	6.6	4	5.2
Totals	76	100.0	76	100.0

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study found that there are several correlations between education level and the view that tax evasion may be justified in certain cases. However, the World Values Survey data provided no further details. Thus, we were not able to determine why individuals at certain education levels thought the way they did, or why there was more than one correlation.

One area for future research would be to delve into more detail to determine the reasons why individuals give the answers that they do. For example, why do some people with a high level of education have a fairly high approval of tax evasion while other do not? Why do people with different education levels think differently about the issue? Why are some correlations positive while others are negative? Why are some correlations curvilinear? More in-depth face-to-face or survey interviews would be able to uncover the answers to these questions.

This study did not examine the relationship of other demographic variables such as gender, age, income level or social class to views on tax evasion. Thus, there is room for further research on this topic.

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